

EMBARCKING ON PHENOMENOLOGICAL TRANSCENDENCE: UNVEILING THE ESSENCE OF LANGUAGE IN IPEd-REVITALIZATION, PRESERVATION AND CHALLENGES

Shielane D. Baba, LPT
Joselyn C. Estrellan, Ph.D.

DEPED Esperanza District III, Sultan Kudarat Division, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Indigenous Peoples' Education (IPEd) is crucial in addressing Indigenous students' educational needs while preserving their languages, cultures, and identities. This qualitative study used a transcendental phenomenological approach to explore the experiences of IPEd teachers in DepEd Esperanza District III, Sultan Kudarat, focusing on language integration and cultural preservation. Fifteen IPEd teachers were purposively selected, and thematic analysis was applied to interview and focus group data. Findings highlight challenges in language revitalization, including a shortage of Indigenous Peoples (IP) teachers. Non-IP teachers face language barriers, limiting effective instruction, and rely on translation as a survival strategy. The lack of culturally relevant materials further complicates teaching. Despite these challenges, teachers' immersion in local communities aids language acquisition, making them key advocates for language preservation. However, remote school locations exacerbate these difficulties. IPEd integrates traditional language practices with modern education, emphasizing the need for culturally relevant lessons incorporating Indigenous languages and knowledge. DepEd supports this through training, writeshops, and collaboration with IP elders. Continued teacher training and cultural programs are essential for language revitalization. This study underscores the need to increase IP teachers, enhance cultural competency, and integrate Indigenous Knowledge Systems into education. Collaborative efforts with IP elders, culturally relevant materials, and ongoing teacher support are vital for preserving language and cultural heritage for future generations.

Keywords: *Language In Iped-Revitalization*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Indigenous Peoples' Education (IPEd) stands as a vital pillar within inclusive educational systems, crucially addressing the academic requirements of Indigenous students while preserving and revitalizing their languages, cultures, and identities. Language, an elemental facet of cultural heritage, is pivotal in IPEd initiatives.

In New Zealand, the Māori language revitalization movement, driven by community efforts and supported by governmental policies, has seen significant success in the last few decades (Higgins & Rewi, 2014). The establishment of Kura Kaupapa Māori (Māori immersion schools) and the official recognition of Māori as an official language have been pivotal in these efforts. Similarly, in Canada, the preservation of First Nations languages has gained momentum with initiatives like the First Peoples' Cultural Council, which supports language documentation, education, and revitalization projects (Ball & McIvor, 2019). These initiatives often face challenges related to funding, resources, and the integration of indigenous languages into mainstream education systems.

However, despite its significance, existing research on IPEd primarily centers on broader scopes, often overlooking in-depth analyses of language's intricate role. Furthermore, these studies frequently fail to evaluate how language integration directly influences the preservation and revitalization of cultures within Indigenous communities (Ngag, 2023). Although the importance of language revitalization is acknowledged, a paucity of comprehensive research exists, particularly in identifying and addressing the challenges encountered during language integration in IPEd settings.

This study is anchored on the International Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP). The UNDRIP, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 2007, recognizes the right of indigenous peoples to revitalize, use, develop, and transmit their languages (Article 13). It emphasizes the importance of linguistic diversity and the right to education that respects cultural identity (Article 14).

Furthermore, the National Cultural Heritage Act of 2009 (Republic Act No. 10066) is a Philippine law that aims to protect, preserve, and promote the nation's cultural heritage and resources. It recognizes the importance of preserving the cultural heritage of the Philippines, including tangible and intangible cultural properties, sites, and artifacts. In the context of IPEd, this highlights the need for partnerships between educational institutions, indigenous communities, government agencies, and other stakeholders to effectively implement language revitalization and preservation initiatives. By involving indigenous communities in decision-making processes and educational programs.

The Department of Education (DepEd), specifically, in Sultan Kudarat, has issued the DepEd Order No. 62, s. 2011, on the Implementing Guidelines on the Integration of Indigenous Peoples' Culture, History, and Values in the K to 12 Curriculum which provides guidance on the integration of indigenous peoples' culture, history, and values across different learning areas in the K to 12 curriculum. It emphasizes the importance of recognizing and respecting the cultural diversity of indigenous communities and incorporating their knowledge systems into the educational process. The order also outlines strategies for curriculum development, teacher training, and community involvement to ensure the effective implementation of the program.

This study aims to address these critical research gaps by exploring the multifaceted roles of language in IPEd. It seeks to investigate language integration into Indigenous education, its impact on cultural preservation, and the obstacles it encounters. By examining these dimensions, this research strives to contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the significance of language within IPEd contexts.

Research Questions

This study explored the role of language in IPEd to understand how language is integrated into Indigenous education, its impact on cultural preservation, and the challenges it encounters among IP schools in DepEd Esperanza III. It answered the following:

1. What personal narratives and challenges do teachers engage in language revitalization efforts within Indigenous, minority, or endangered language communities within the context of IPEd in DepEd Esperanza District III?
2. How do language revitalization initiatives within IPEd contexts reconcile traditional language practices with contemporary challenges and opportunities in DepEd Esperanza District III?
3. What are the transcendental aspects of language revitalization efforts, and how do they contribute to the preservation and transmission of cultural heritage within IPEd communities in DepEd Esperanza District III?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design, specifically the transcendental phenomenological approach, to explore the teachers' lived experiences in implementing language in Indigenous Peoples' Education (IPEd). This approach is particularly suitable for the study because it emphasizes understanding the essence of experiences as perceived by individuals directly involved in the phenomenon.

The transcendental phenomenological approach is scientifically justified in this study because it provides a robust framework for exploring complex, subjective

experiences, such as those related to implementing language policies in culturally sensitive educational settings (Battiste, 2013). By focusing on the lived experiences of IPEd teachers, the approach enables the researcher to capture how language integration impacts cultural preservation and the challenges educators face in this unique context (Moustakas, 1994). It aligns with phenomenology's goal to uncover the meaning and significance of experiences from the perspective of those who live them rather than imposing external interpretations or frameworks.

Additionally, this approach allows for exploring shared experiences among teachers, revealing common themes and patterns that can inform the development of more effective language integration strategies in IPEd. By employing transcendental phenomenology, the study contributes to the broader understanding of how indigenous languages can be effectively preserved and revitalized within educational systems, addressing a significant gap in local and international research on culturally responsive education (Creswell, 2013).

Respondents of the Study

Table 1 displays the qualifications of the participants based on the criteria set by the researcher prior to the selection of qualified informants of the study.

Table 1

Participants' Inclusion Criteria

Qualifications
<i>Participants: 15 Teachers</i>
<p>Current Employment Status</p> <p><i>- Participants must be regular Indigenous Peoples Education teachers of Department of Education (DepEd) Esperanza District III, Sultan Kudarat.</i></p> <p>Minimum Teaching Experience</p> <p><i>Participants should have a minimum of three to ten years of teaching experience assigned to mountainous schools in DepEd Esperanza District III. Must have experience handling Indigenous Peoples learners.</i></p> <p>Willingness to Participate in Narrative Inquiry</p>

Participants must be willing to share their personal experiences and motivations through narrative inquiry methods, including interviews.

The participants of this study were the selected ten (15) teachers who are assigned in Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) implementing schools, who qualify the inclusion criteria set by the researcher.

Sampling Technique

During the conduct, a purposive sampling technique was intentionally utilized to carefully select the IPEd teachers from elementary and secondary schools in DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria established by the researcher.

This purposive sampling method is particularly effective in studies where the goal is to explore specific phenomena in depth, as it allows the researcher to focus on informants who are most knowledgeable about the topic (Creswell & Poth, 2018). By selecting participants who met these predefined qualifications, the study ensured that the data collected was relevant and reliable, contributing to the overall validity of the research findings.

This sampling method mandated that researchers possess prior knowledge of the objectives underpinning their study to effectively pinpoint and contact eligible participants through online survey platforms (Ronquillo & Ngag, 2024). Researchers resort to purposive sampling to secure access to a distinct subgroup of individuals, whereby all survey respondents were meticulously chosen based on their alignment with a specific demographic or criterion.

Research Instruments

In this study, a semi-structured interview was the primary investigative tool employed during interviews. The objective was to examine the role of language in IPEd to understand how language was integrated into Indigenous education, its impact on cultural preservation, and the challenges it encounters among IPEd-implementing schools in DepEd Esperanza III.

The researcher documented the study's results through detailed transcription of the interviews. Each interview and discussion were recorded and transcribed verbatim to ensure capturing participants' responses accurately.

The researcher met the LGU and the municipal Indigenous Peoples` Mandatory Representative (IPMR) in the target locale of her study. Interpretation of the results involved thematic analysis, which identified recurring themes, patterns, and insights related to the role of language in Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd). This analysis was conducted systematically, carefully examining the nuances and meanings expressed by participants during the In-Depth Interviews.

The findings were presented in a comprehensive report that outlines the key themes and insights derived from the data. This report included direct quotes from participants to illustrate important points and provide context for the findings. Visual aids such as charts, graphs, or tables may also present quantitative data.

Additionally, the researcher considered organizing a presentation or seminar to disseminate the findings to relevant stakeholders, such as educators, policymakers, and community members involved in Indigenous education. It provided an opportunity to discuss the implications of the findings and explore potential strategies for addressing the challenges identified in the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

To ensure the research's reliability, the researcher adhered strictly to a predefined set of procedures. The primary objective of this study was to examine the role of language in IPEd to understand how it was integrated into Indigenous education, its impact on cultural preservation, and the challenges it encountered among IPEd-implementing schools in DepEd Esperanza III.

In the initial phase, the researcher sought formal authorization from the Dean of the Graduate School and the Superintendent of DepEd-Sultan Kudarat. This authorization was essential to obtain permission for the researcher to conduct the study, emphasizing the importance of ethical considerations.

A secondary authorization letter was sent to the District Supervisor, explicitly requesting access to the specific data required for this research. A meticulously crafted survey questionnaire was developed, subjected to rigorous evaluation, and administered to the targeted participants.

The researcher employed a purposive sampling technique to carefully select elementary and secondary school teachers as participants in this study. Assuming strict adherence to established health protocols, the researcher conducted an In-Depth interview through face-to-face interactions.

Ultimately, the data collected from interviews were systematically organized, comprehensively analyzed, and interpreted using the thematic analysis approach. This approach was expected to provide a deeper understanding of the issues under investigation. See the diagram below:

Figure 3. Data Gathering Procedure of the Study

Data Transcription Process

All gathered raw data from the participants through interviews and FGDs were transcribed using the transcription process of Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). By following these step-by-step processes, the researcher aligned their transcription approach with the guidelines outlined by Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). This rigorous transcription process ensured the trustworthiness and credibility of the qualitative data, which served as the foundation for the subsequent narrative analysis and the meaningful interpretation of the gathered raw data.

In the context of the study on the essence of language in IPEd-revitalization, preservation and challenges of teachers in Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who have experience teaching in the IPEd implementing schools, the steps in the transcription process were outlined as follows:

Step 1: Audio Recording of Interviews

The first step in the transcription process involved audio recording interviews with the participants. For this study, researchers conducted in-depth interviews with teachers in Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who have experience teaching in the IPEd implementing schools. These interviews were recorded with explicit consent from the participants (Ngag, 2023).

Step 2: Verbatim Transcription

Verbatim transcription was crucial as it captured participants' responses exactly as spoken, including pauses, hesitations, and emotional expressions. The researcher meticulously transcribed the audio recordings, ensuring to preserve the precise language, grammatical structures, and speech patterns of the participants interviewed.

Step 3: Researcher Verification

After transcription, the researcher verified the accuracy of transcripts by carefully reviewing them for any discrepancies or omissions. This step ensured that the written text faithfully represented the original audio recordings and maintained the integrity of the data collected.

Step 4: Participant Validation

Following transcription, the researcher shared the transcripts with participants for their review and feedback. Participants had the opportunity to validate the accuracy of their recorded responses, providing insights or clarifications where necessary. This process ensured that participants' perspectives were accurately represented in the study.

Step 5: Anonymization

To protect participants' confidentiality, the researcher anonymized transcripts by replacing any identifying information, such as names or specific locations, with pseudonyms or generic descriptors. This precautionary measure safeguarded the privacy of young learners involved in the study.

Data Analysis

A thematic or content analysis was used to analyze the data. By assigning each text's assertions, phrases, and words to a system or collection of categories—either based on or adapted from existing ones or established from scratch in connection to the study objectives—is what Flick (2014) calls "content" or "thematic" analysis.

Written interview data was collected from the participants to determine the experiences and motivations of teachers in the essence of language in IPEd-revitalization, preservation and challenges of teachers in Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who have experience teaching in the IPEd implementing schools. The in-depth interviews conducted for this research will be used to distill the most salient participant answers into overarching themes.

Scope and Limitations

The study focused on schools and Indigenous communities within DepEd Esperanza District III, considering their linguistic diversity, cultural heritage, and educational settings. It examined multiple Indigenous languages spoken within the district, exploring their roles, status, usage, and potential endangerment.

The study delved into incorporating Indigenous languages within the educational framework, including formal IPEd programs, language-in-education policies, and language teaching methodologies. It analyzed the relationship between language and cultural practices, emphasizing how language revitalization contributes to preserving Indigenous cultural heritage.

The study assessed the existing policies, strategies, and initiatives related to language revitalization and preservation within the educational system of DepEd Esperanza District III. The study focused on data collection and analysis during the school year 2024-2025, limiting its investigation to a specific period due to time constraints.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Indigenous Peoples' Education (IPEd) stands as a vital pillar within inclusive educational systems, crucially addressing the academic requirements of Indigenous students while preserving and revitalizing their languages, cultures, and identities. In this study, qualitative research, specifically the transcendental phenomenological approach, was employed to examine the lived-experiences of the teachers in the implementation of language in IPEd. It also explored how teachers understand the integration of language

into Indigenous education, including its impact on cultural preservation, and the challenges it encounters among IP schools in DepEd Esperanza III.

The study involved fifteen (15) IPED teachers from among elementary and secondary schools in DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria. A Purposive Sampling Technique was intentionally utilized to carefully select the IPED teachers from elementary and secondary schools in DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat. The research took place within the jurisdiction of DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat. Situating the research within the DepEd Esperanza District III jurisdiction narrows the focus to a specific educational administrative unit. Thematic Analysis was utilized to analyze the relevant data from interviews.

Result showed a significant issue is the shortage of Indigenous Peoples (IP) teachers, with non-IP teachers struggling to connect with students due to language barriers, which limits effective lesson delivery. Non-IP teachers are required to learn indigenous languages to enhance communication, while many rely on translation as a survival strategy to facilitate understanding. Additionally, teachers face challenges in adapting to indigenous languages, with the lack of culturally relevant teaching materials further hindering the process. Teachers' personal experiences reveal the need for increased cultural competency, and their immersion in local communities helps them gradually acquire language skills, positioning them as crucial advocates in language preservation. However, these efforts are often complicated by the remote location of many schools, which intensifies the language barriers and further complicates revitalization efforts. Overall, the findings underscored the importance of addressing these challenges to improve the effectiveness of language revitalization in Indigenous communities.

The reconciliation of language revitalization initiatives within the IPED framework represents a thoughtful integration of traditional language practices with modern educational challenges and opportunities. The result revealed that the initiative focused on bridging the gap between traditional cultural practices and contemporary education by ensuring academic and culturally relevant lessons.

By contextualizing lessons to incorporate Indigenous languages, knowledge systems, and cultural practices, educators enhance students' understanding and connection to the content. DepEd further supported this integration by facilitating the development of culturally relevant learning materials through training and writing shops, strengthening the cultural connection in education. Continuous teacher training and support were pivotal in addressing challenges and ensuring the successful implementation of language revitalization efforts. Collaboration with IP elders and cultural programs underscored the importance of preserving language and cultural heritage. At the same time, it was crucial to refine strategies and address the remaining challenges in effectively integrating Indigenous languages into modern education.

Finally, the transcendental aspects of language revitalization efforts in DepEd Esperanza District III highlight the significant role of language preservation in fostering cultural heritage and identity among Indigenous Peoples. These efforts emphasized the importance of integrating Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSPs) into education, allowing IP learners to retain their cultural pride while enhancing their self-esteem. Teachers and educational personnel prioritize revitalizing IP languages, connecting them to cultural identity, spirituality, and ancestral roots. Collaborative efforts with IP elders ensure cultural knowledge and language transmission, preserving traditions for future generations.

Furthermore, the IPEd program aligns with DepEd's mission to offer inclusive education while promoting culturally responsive teaching approaches that respect and preserve IP learners' diverse linguistic and cultural identities. Cultural celebrations and pride-building activities further strengthen the connection between language and cultural preservation, enabling students to actively contribute to safeguarding their heritage.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were made in light of this study's findings:

The shortage of Indigenous Peoples (IP) teachers in DepEd Esperanza District III significantly hampers the effectiveness of language revitalization efforts. Non-IP teachers face communication barriers due to language differences, which limits their ability to effectively engage with students. Increased cultural competency, teacher training, and immersion in local communities are necessary to address these challenges and facilitate the preservation of indigenous languages and cultures.

The reconciliation of language revitalization efforts within the Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) framework in DepEd Esperanza District III demonstrates a thoughtful approach to integrating Indigenous cultural practices with modern educational needs. By contextualizing lessons and developing culturally relevant materials, DepEd bridges the gap between traditional knowledge and contemporary education. Teacher training, continuous support, and collaboration with IP elders are essential in preserving Indigenous languages and fostering a culturally connected learning environment.

The transcendental aspects of language revitalization efforts underscore the critical role of language in preserving cultural heritage and identity among Indigenous Peoples. By incorporating Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSPs) into education, students retain their cultural pride while enhancing their self-esteem. Collaborative efforts with IP elders, culturally responsive teaching methods, and the promotion of cultural celebrations all contribute to the transmission of language and traditions, ensuring that future generations are empowered to safeguard their heritage.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings, the following were recommended:

1. **DepEd may** prioritize the recruitment and hiring of Indigenous Peoples (IP) teachers who are fluent in local languages and culturally competent. This will reduce language barriers and foster a deeper connection between teachers and students, enhancing the effectiveness of lesson delivery. Develop and implement continuous professional development programs focused on cultural competency and language acquisition for non-IP teachers. Teachers should receive regular training to enhance their skills in communicating with IP students and integrating Indigenous knowledge and practices into their lessons. Ensure the development and distribution of teaching materials that are culturally relevant, context-specific, and incorporate Indigenous languages, knowledge systems, and cultural practices. This will facilitate better engagement with IP learners and reinforce their connection to their heritage. Continue to align the IPED framework with the goal of fostering inclusive education that respects and promotes Indigenous cultures and languages. Encourage the integration of traditional practices with modern educational challenges, ensuring a holistic learning experience for IP learners.

2. **District Supervisors may** encourage collaboration between teachers, IP elders, and culture bearers to integrate authentic Indigenous knowledge into the curriculum. Elders may play an active role in curriculum planning and classroom activities to ensure the transmission of cultural practices and language. Address the challenges faced by schools in remote areas by providing logistical support for teachers to attend training and access resources. Consider establishing partnerships with local communities to facilitate the acquisition of language skills by teachers. Implement regular monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the progress of language revitalization initiatives. This will help identify gaps and areas for improvement, allowing for timely interventions.

3. **Policy Makers may** develop policies that prioritize the inclusion of Indigenous languages in the national curriculum and ensure adequate resources are allocated to support language revitalization efforts. Policies should also promote the hiring of IP teachers and the development of culturally responsive educational practices. Support research initiatives that focus on the challenges and best practices in language revitalization. This research should inform the development of policies and strategies that better address the needs of IP communities in education.

4. **IP Community may engage in Language Revitalization Efforts.** Encourage the active participation of community members, including elders and culture bearers, in preserving and transmitting Indigenous languages and cultural practices. Their involvement in educational activities will ensure that the community's heritage is preserved for future generations. Organize and participate in cultural celebrations, language workshops, and educational programs that reinforce the importance of language and culture in the community. This will help build pride and commitment to preserving Indigenous languages.

5. **Future Researchers may** focus on the long-term effects of language revitalization programs on the academic achievement and cultural identity of IP learners. Studies should also examine the impact of teacher training and community involvement on the success of language preservation efforts. Explore how digital tools and platforms can be

utilized to support language learning and cultural transmission in remote communities. Research can identify innovative solutions that bridge gaps in access to resources and help teachers and students engage more effectively in language revitalization.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Teachers assigned to mountainous schools are often attuned to IP communities' cultural contexts and specific challenges. Cultural competence is essential for educators to create inclusive learning environments that respect and integrate their learners' cultural identities (Gay, 2010). This understanding fosters an educational atmosphere conducive to learners' learning.

Before commencing this study, it is essential to underline the critical significance of ethical considerations within the research focused on the role of language in IPEd to understand how language is integrated into Indigenous education, its impact on cultural preservation, and the challenges it encounters among IPEd implementing schools in DepEd Esperanza III (Ngag, 2023).

To prepare for implementation, we presented the plans and recommendations to Sultan Kudarat State University to ensure adherence to prescribed procedures and protocols. Consequently, the following ethical principles were emphasized:

Informed Consent. Before participation, explicit and informed consent was diligently obtained from all school heads involved in the study. They must comprehensively understand the study's objectives, methodologies, potential risks, and benefits. Furthermore, participation remained entirely voluntary, allowing participants to withdraw from the study at any juncture without encountering any adverse consequences.

Anonymity and Confidentiality. To safeguard the teachers' identities and responses, rigorous measures were enacted to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. Rather than actual names, pseudonyms or codes were employed, upholding the participants' privacy. The data collected was securely stored, with access restricted solely to the research team.

Avoiding Harm. Delicate subjects, such as the challenges inherent in their roles, were discussed with meticulous consideration for the potential emotional and psychological impact on the participants. Strategies were in place to minimize distress, and a support system readily assisted participants should the need arise (Magonsik & Ngag, 2025).

Researcher-Participant Relationship. The researcher maintained a professional and respectful rapport with the school heads. Any actions that may exploit or cause harm to the participants were carefully avoided, ensuring their utmost dignity and respect throughout the research process.

Data Protection. Adherence to data protection regulations and laws was unwaveringly followed to safeguard the participants' personal information. Stringent measures were employed to ensure data's secure storage and transmission.

Voluntary Participation. Participants were assured that their involvement in the study was wholly voluntary and devoid of any form of coercion or external pressure (Ngag, 2023).

Researcher Bias. The researcher remained vigilant regarding potential biases that might influence data collection and analysis, upholding objectivity and transparency throughout the research.

Institutional Approval. Before initiating the study, the researcher obtained ethical clearance from the pertinent institutional review boards or ethics committees.

Honesty and Integrity. The research findings were reported truthfully and accurately, without manipulation or distortion, to align with preconceived notions or biases.

Beneficence. The potential benefits of this research to educational practices and policies, particularly for the Teduray and Dulangan Manobo beneficiaries, were thoughtfully considered. The study aims to contribute positively by enhancing the education system, specifically by developing culturally responsive teaching practices and policies that honor and preserve the Teduray and Dulangan Manobo language and culture. This focus ensures that the research informs broader educational practices and directly benefits the Teduray and Dulangan Manobo communities by addressing their unique academic needs and promoting the revitalizing of their cultural heritage within the educational framework.

Cultural Sensitivity. The researcher displayed cultural sensitivity by respecting Teduray and Dulangan Manobo's customs, beliefs, and practices within the research setting, refraining from imposing external values on the participants.

Inclusion and Diversity. The research design prioritized inclusivity and diversity, encompassing a broad range of implementations of Indigenous Peoples Education. By diligently upholding these ethical principles, the study was carried out conscientiously and with due regard to the rights and welfare of the IP students involved. Concurrently, it offered valuable contributions to the field of education, particularly within the unique setting of DepEd Sultan Kudarat, specifically focusing on the welfare of IP schools.

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